

Measurement Tool for The Influence of Sales Promotion, Utilitarian Motive, Self Esteem Motive, and Hedonic Motive on Purchase Decision with Impulse Buying and Behavior Intention as Variable Intervening in E-commerce XYZ

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ABSTRACT: One proof of the ease of technology is the emergence of e-commerce. E-commerce is a medium that allows sellers and buyers to meet face-to-face. This research aims to provide a measurement tool to analyze the influence of sales promotion, utilitarian motive, self-esteem, and hedonic motive on purchasing decisions with impulse buying and behavioral intention as intervening variables. This research surveyed with the participation of 30 respondents who had purchased products through XYZ e-commerce. Therefore, this measuring instrument meets the requirements and is acceptable for further research.

KEYWORDS: Behavior Intention, Hedonic Motive, Impulse Buying, Purchase Decision, Sales Promotion, Self Esteem, Utilitarian.

INTRODUCTION

One proof of the ease of technology is the emergence of e-commerce. E-commerce is a medium that allows sellers and buyers to meet face-to-face. E-commerce success cannot be separated from several factors, one of which is Sales Promotion. Sales promotion is a type of marketing activity that is usually used to introduce new products, sell old products, and of course increase sales. Sales promotion can influence price sensitivity and consumer willingness. Well-executed offers that offer significant discounts or savings opportunities can make purchasing decisions more attractive, especially for price-sensitive consumers. There is a link between sales promotions and purchasing decisions, which is explained by research (I Nyoman, 2022) explaining that sales promotions have a significant influence on purchasing decisions.

Many factors influence the consumer shopping process. One of them is impulse buying. By opening an online platform, there is a big possibility that consumers will buy goods impulsively. Promotions in e-commerce offered also encourage impulse buying e-commerce which offers consumers more convenience in getting a shopping experience. The rapid growth of the digital business market (e-commerce) currently increases the risk of shopping addiction, especially in digitally savvy communities like Indonesia.

In the context of online shopping, utilitarian motives refer to purchasing an item because of its functional value, while hedonic motives refer to the emotional experience of the online shopping process itself (Indrawati, 2023). Utilitarian motives can have an influence on impulse purchasing and behavioral intentions in e-commerce. Impulse buying refers to unplanned purchasing decisions made by consumers, often driven by emotional or hedonistic factors rather than careful consideration. On the other hand, utilitarian motives refer to the practical and functional aspects of a purchase, such as fulfilling a particular need or solving a problem with that consumer's needs.

The term Self Esteem Motive in the consumer context refers to how consumers feel about themselves by purchasing certain products or utilizing services because consumers tend to buy appropriate products for themselves to make themselves feel special (Indrawati, 2023). Self Esteem Motive refers to an individual's evaluation of their own self-worth and worth.

Individuals who have high self-esteem take actions to further affirm their self-worth, values, and standards. The theory of planned behavior posits that consumers will behave in certain ways to achieve desired consequences. (Indrawati, 2023). Individuals with low self-esteem may engage in impulse buying to seek emotional satisfaction and increase their self-esteem. Obtaining a new product or enjoying shopping can provide temporary feelings of happiness or satisfaction, which can offset feelings of inadequacy or low self-esteem. In e-commerce, the ease, convenience of online shopping and the availability of a wide range of products can facilitate impulse purchasing decisions driven by self-esteem motives. Therefore, in this research, the self-esteem motive is expected to direct consumers to carry out online shopping behavior.

The influence of hedonic motives on impulse purchasing and behavioral intentions in e-commerce can be significant. Hedonic motives refer to the desire for sensory pleasure, enjoyment, and emotional satisfaction that comes from the shopping experience and the product itself. The development of the web environment, along with its continued use by consumers, has resulted in enjoyable experiences and even excitement in the purchasing process. (Indrawati, 2023). Online shopping platforms often offer a variety of exciting features and personalized recommendations that enhance the pleasure-seeking aspect of the shopping experience. Consumers may engage in impulse purchases driven by the desire for immediate gratification and enjoyment of exploring new products, browsing visually appealing content, and discovering new or interesting items. Hedonic motives can cause impulsive purchases and influence behavioral intentions because consumers seek pleasurable experiences through the act of shopping itself.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Sales Promotion

According to Kotler and Keller (2022:282), sales promotions are the main key in carrying out marketing campaigns which consist of a collection of short-term incentive tools, most of which are designed by traders so that consumers can purchase certain products or services more quickly.

B. Utilitarian Motive

In the context of online shopping, utilitarian motives relate to purchasing an object because of its functional value, while hedonic motives concern the emotional experience of the online shopping process itself (Indrawati, 2023).

C. Self Esteem Motive

Self-Esteem Motive is an individual's assessment of himself which is manifested in positive and negative attitudes. Self-Esteem Motive refers to how valuing oneself influences daily life. Self-esteem motives can influence purchasing decisions by trying to express and strengthen one's self-image or desired social identity. Recent research also confirms that consumers also seek psychological and social benefits in purchasing products (Indrawati, 2023)..

D. Hedonic Motive

Simultaneously, (Indrawati, 2023) emphasized the importance of hedonic motives in increasing the impulsive shopping tendencies of online buyers based on the ease and comfort provided by digital media channels.

E. Impulse Buying

According to Amos (2014), impulse buying refers to unplanned buying behavior characterized by relatively quick decision making and a desire to own.

F. Behavior Intention

Behavioral Intention refers to an individual's conscious decision and willingness to engage in a particular behavior. (Indrawati, 2023)

G. Conceptual Framework Model

This image is a framework for thinking based on the hypothesis discussed previously

METHOD

This research expands and combines several previous studies. This research uses seven variables which are divided into dependent, independent, and intervening variables, each variable consisting of several indicators. The dependent variable consists of purchase decisions with 12 indicators (Angraini et al., 2019). The independent variable is sales promotion with 9 indicators (Prasetio & Muchnita, 2022); utilitarian motive with 5 indicators (Indrawati et al, 2023); self-esteem motive with 5 indicators (Indrawati et al, 2023); hedonic motive with 5 indicators (Indrawati et al, 2023). The intervening variable consists of Impulse buying with 13 indicators (Indrawati et al, 2023); behavior intention with 4 indicators (Indrawati et al, 2023). The following Table 1 presents the measurements of the variables studied as follows:

Variable	Indicator	Item
Sales Promotion (X1)	XYZ provides free coupons (for example: coupons	SP1
	I will buy products that I have never bought before because of the coupons given by XYZ.	SP2
	I will exchange the coupon provided when making a purchase via XYZ	SP3
	XYZ provides attractive cashback or refunds	SP4
	The cashback program offered by XYZ can make me buy more products than I planned	SP5
	Cashback on XYZ is easy to use	SP6
	I like the bundling price offered by XYZ	SP7
	XYZ's bundling price offer is very attractive	SP8
	I feel that XYZ's bundling prices are very effective	SP9
Utilitarian Motive (X2)	I browse XYZ to buy items that are better in price or quality	UM1
	I am looking for XYZ for efficient online shopping	UM2
	I browsed the XYZ website to gather information about the product	UM3
	I browsed the XYZ site while shopping to comparison shop	UM4
	I browse various stores on XYZ to get as much added value as possible	UM5
Self esteem Motive (X3)	Sometimes I think I'm very good at a lot of things	SM1
	I feel like I have a lot to be proud of	SM2
	I feel useless at times	SM3
	I wish I could appreciate myself more	SM4
	Overall, I tend to think that I failed	SM5
Hedonic Motive (X4)	When browsing XYZ, I can forget about my problems	HM1
	While browsing XYZ, I was very excited, like playing	HM2
	When browsing XYZ, I feel comfortable	HM3
	I enjoy browsing XYZ enough to forget about downtime	HM4
	I browse items on XYZ just for fun	HM5
Purchase Decision (Z)	I will buy products on XYZ.	PD1
	XYZ offers a variety of products and services that suit my needs.	PD2
	XYZ offers superior products and services	PD3
	I chose XYZ because there are many choices of products from various brands.	PD4
	XYZ has quality brands.	PD5

Impulse Buying (Y1)	The price offers on XYZ are appropriate	PD6
	By shopping using the XYZ application, I can check how many products I need	PD7
	XYZ has enough products and services for consumers to buy.	PD8
	I can always shop with XYZ	PD9
	I make repeat purchases over some time.	PD10
	The XYZ application offers payment methods that are easy to use and understand	PD11
	I feel safe with the XYZ payment process.	PD12
	It's hard to leave behind the good stuff I see on XYZ	IB1
	I sometimes can't help but feel like buying something on XYZ	IB2
	If I buy something on XYZ, I usually do it spontaneously	IB3
	I sometimes feel guilty after buying something on XYZ	IB4
	I can get very excited if I see something I want to buy on XYZ	IB5
	I always see something fun every time I visit some shop on XYZ	IB6
Bahavior Intention (Y2)	I find it hard to miss discounted items on XYZ	IB7
	If I see something new on XYZ, I want to buy it	IB8
	I'm a bit careless when buying things on XYZ	IB9
	I sometimes buy things on XYZ because I like buying things, not because I need them	IB10
	I buy things according to how I feel at the moment	IB11
	I carefully plan most of my purchases	IB12
	I often buy things without consulting other people	IB13
	I often buy products online at XYZ	BI1
	I buy products online every day	BI2
	When I need a product, I buy it online at XYZ	BI3
	I buy products online on XYZ almost every day	BI4

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Questionnaires were distributed online using Google Forms to respondents with 30 respondents.

Characteristic		Frequency (N=30)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	12	40%
	Female	18	60%
Age	26 years old	13	43%
	25 years old	6	20%
	24 years old	2	6,6%
	23 years old	4	13,3%
	22 years old	1	3,9%
	21 years old	0	0%
	20 years old	2	6,6%
	19 years old	0	0%
Profession	18 years old	2	6,6%
	Student	9	30%
	Private employed	6	20%

Last Education	Self-employed	8	26,6%
	Civil Servant	4	13,4%
	other	3	10%
Monthly Income	Master Degree	5	16,6%
	Bachelor Degree	16	53,4%
	Diploma	4	13,4%
Monthly Income	Senior High School	5	16,6%
	< Rp 3.000.000	12	40%
	Rp 3.000.000 – Rp 5.000.000	6	20%
	Rp. 5.000.001 – Rp 7.000.000	7	23,3%
	Rp.7.000.001 – Rp 10.000.000	3	10%
	>Rp. 10.000.000	2	6,7%

The author first conducted a pilot study to test the questionnaire so that this research was truly valid to be applied in further research. This trial involved 30 respondents for initial data. Data collected from 30 consumers who have made purchases at XYZ e-commerce. Indrawati (2015) states that validity will show the extent to which a measuring instrument can measure what it wants to measure, so in other words the higher the level of validity of the measuring instrument, the more it will be in line with its target or can clarify what should be measured. In determining whether each instrument is declared valid or not, you can compare the r table with the calculated r with a significance value of 5%. This means that if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ then the research statement instrument is declared valid, and conversely if $r_{count} < r_{table}$ then the research statement instrument is declared invalid. The r table value for $N = 30$ with a significance level of 5% or $\alpha = 0.05$ is obtained at 0.361.

According to Indrawati (2015:155), the reliability test is used to show how far the measurement results are free from measurement error. Reliability testing can be carried out for all statements or statement items together. Reliability testing aims to ensure that respondents answer the questionnaire consistently. If the alpha value is > 0.70 then it is reliable

Variable	Item	Validity Test		Reliability Test	
		r-stat	Decision	Cronbach's Alpha	Decision
Sales Promotion	SP 1	0,822	Valid	0.927	Reliable
	SP 2	0,768	Valid		
	SP 3	0,766	Valid		
	SP 4	0,802	Valid		
	SP 5	0,844	Valid		
	SP 6	0,776	Valid		
	SP 7	0,816	Valid		
	SP 8	0,799	Valid		
	SP 9	0,771	Valid		
Utilitarian Motive	UM 1	0,986	Valid	0.973	Reliable
	UM 2	0,935	Valid		
	UM 3	0,928	Valid		
	UM 4	0,935	Valid		
	UM 5	0,986	Valid		
Self-esteem Motive	SM 1	0,885	Valid	0.928	Reliable
	SM 2	0,848	Valid		
	SM 3	0,896	Valid		
	SM 4	0,856	Valid		
	SM 5	0,939	Valid		

<i>Hedonic Motive</i>	HM 1	0,882	Valid	0.916	Reliable
	HM 2	0,826	Valid		
	HM 3	0,912	Valid		
	HM 4	0,868	Valid		
	HM 5	0,843	Valid		
<i>Purchase Decision</i>	PD 1	0,926	Valid	0.986	Reliable
	PD 2	0,946	Valid		
	PD 3	0,987	Valid		
	PD 4	0,968	Valid		
	PD 5	0,971	Valid		
	PD 6	0,933	Valid		
	PD 7	0,937	Valid		
	PD 8	0,943	Valid		
	PD 9	0,902	Valid		
	PD 10	0,928	Valid		
	PD 11	0,862	Valid		
	PD 12	0,953	Valid		
<i>Impulse Buying</i>	IB 1	0,868	Valid	0.969	Reliable
	IB 2	0,869	Valid		
	IB 3	0,840	Valid		
	IB 4	0,894	Valid		
	IB 5	0,870	Valid		
	IB 6	0,872	Valid		
	IB 7	0,804	Valid		
	IB 8	0,877	Valid		
	IB 9	0,809	Valid		
	IB 10	0,852	Valid		
	IB 11	0,742	Valid		
	IB 12	0,795	Valid		
	IB 13	0,896	Valid		
<i>Behaviour Intention</i>	BI 1	0,869	Valid	0.912	Reliable
	BI 2	0,903	Valid		
	BI 3	0,869	Valid		
	BI 4	0,942	Valid		

Based on this table, it can be seen that all statement items for the measurement variables have values above the r-table (0.361), so that all statement items can be said to be valid. Meanwhile, the reliability test results show a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.7 so that all variables can be declared reliable.

CONCLUSION

The measurement material used in this research has been tested on 30 consumer respondents who have made purchases at XYZ e-commerce. The results of this research prove that the instrument consisting of 7 variables and 53 items is valid and reliable. Therefore, the proposed measurement model can be used in further research. Based on the table above, it can be seen that all statement items for variables have values above r table (0.361), so that all statement items can be said to be valid. Then the reliability test results show the Cronbach Alpha value > 0.7 so that all variables can be declared reliable.

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